

GLOBE Observer Eclipse Summary

GLOBE Observer Eclipse 2023-2024

The NASA Earth Science Education Collaborative focused efforts on GLOBE Observer Eclipse in 2023-2024 to achieve the following objectives:

- Use the annular and total eclipses to engage new and diverse audiences in NASA Earth science with an emphasis on the Sun-Earth connection and Earth's energy budget.
- Engage a wide range of community partners to recruit and support a volunteer community
- Collect cloud, temperature, and land cover data to support student and scientific research associated with eclipses.

GLOBE Observer App Updates

- Added Land Cover observation to site set up
- Improved accessibility and offline functionality
- Translated for Spanish, Portuguese, and French
- Added unique eclipse paths

Eclipse Products

- Resource toolkits for Informal educators, volunteers, and media
- [Landing page](#)
- 9 video explainers in English and Spanish
- 4 handouts
- 2 worksheets, tips for student research
- Signs, presentation, tips for events

Engaging and Supporting Partners

- 25 partners engaged
- 3 partners distributed physical material for NESEC
- 19 partners distributed information and digital resources to their audiences
- NESEC provided GLOBE Eclipse training to 18 partners
- NESEC co-hosted training with 5 partners
- For both eclipses, 64% of all data came from partner teams.

Engaging Volunteers Directly

- 34 presentations to audiences (students, life long learners, scientists, decision makers and public)
- 11 eclipse tabling events (not counting NASA SunSpot events)
- Social media engagement through NASA flagship, NASA Earth, NASA Climate, NASA Espanol, and GLOBE social media platform reach more than 2.2 million
- 48 news articles, 7 NASA features, and 1000 views of media kit

Data Collected

- 60,613 air temperature data points
- 34,345 air temperature data points excluding weather station data
- 761 land cover observations
- 25,400 cloud observations
- 421 new volunteers for October eclipse
- 2,605 new volunteers for April eclipse

Clouds on October 14, 2023

Clouds on April 8, 2024

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Report Purpose and Acknowledgements

This document gathers eclipse-related activities into a single document to sum up the extensive efforts of the NASA Earth Science Education Collaborative during the October 2023 and April 2024 eclipses. It is meant to be an internal reference document to serve as a foundation for presentations, condensed summary reports, and publications.

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Background

[GLOBE Eclipse](#) was designed to help individuals appreciate the Sun-Earth connection by observing changes in temperature and clouds during a solar eclipse. The GLOBE Eclipse tool is part of the GLOBE Observer app and has been made available in regions that experienced an eclipse in 2017 (United States), 2019 and 2020 (South America), and 2023 and 2024 (North America). The tool combines GLOBE Clouds (also a GLOBE Observer tool that operates all the time) with a simple interface for recording temperature. Starting in 2023, the protocol also included documenting land cover at the beginning of the observation.

GLOBE Eclipse launched for the 2017 total solar eclipse in the United States. During that eclipse, more than 10,000 observers collected 20,000+ cloud observations with 60,000 photos and 80,000 air temperature measurements. Eclipses in South America in 2019 and 2020 resulted in just over 2,500 temperature measurements and 300 cloud observations. Following the success of their 2017 Eclipse engagement in the United States, the NASA Earth Science Education Collaborative decided to implement GLOBE Eclipse in the GLOBE Observer app for eclipses in 2023 and 2024. Evaluation results from the 2017 eclipse reported that many of the volunteers who joined to participate in the eclipse dropped out, not knowing they could continue their participation in GLOBE through GLOBE Observer. With these results in mind, NESEC altered its approach to recruiting and supporting volunteers in 2023 and 2024 with the intent to retain more volunteers.

Collecting Data Using the GLOBE Eclipse Protocol

For full participation in data collection during eclipses volunteers are asked to start collecting data one to two hours before maximum eclipse through an hour after maximum eclipse. At the beginning of the observation period, the volunteer enters information about their site including thermometer type, temperature scale (Celsius or Fahrenheit), and location. To record land cover

conditions, volunteers take photos of their surroundings, one of which includes the location of the thermometer. Following set up, the volunteer enters their first temperature and cloud observation. The app then reminds volunteers to repeat the temperature observations every 10 minutes and clouds every 30. At 30 minutes before totality, the volunteers are asked to increase frequency of temperature observations to every five minutes and clouds to every 15 minutes until 30 minutes after maximum eclipse with a break at maximum eclipse. Thirty minutes after the maximum eclipse, the reminder frequency returned to 10 minutes for temperature and 30 minutes for clouds.

The Eclipse tool was made available in English, Spanish, and Portuguese for the 2023 eclipse, and English, Spanish and French for 2024. The Clouds tool is always available in all four of those languages.

Partnership Approach to Recruit and Support Volunteers

As in prior years, we made efforts to recruit individual volunteers as described in the communication section, but we expended more energy in developing partnerships with community-based organizations and educators. We did this to provide a local center for volunteers to get support and build connections to other volunteers. We hoped that this type of community would create structures to encourage long-term engagement with collecting data using the GLOBE Observer app.

Products for Partnerships

This partnership approach is reflected in the products created for the eclipse. While a handful of products, such as a how-to video and certificates, were made to support individuals, the majority were created to support partners. Resources designed to support individual observers are starred in the list below, and these resources were also valued by partners. The partner-focused resources were meant to facilitate programming around GLOBE Eclipse and include display materials, presentation slides, data sheets for groups, and more.

- Most products were distributed in both English and [Spanish](#), and some were translated into [French](#), as the 2024 eclipse path included portions of French-speaking Canada. All resources were designed to be fully accessible.
- Products were distributed in three spaces on the GLOBE Observer website: a [toolkit for informal educators](#), a [resource library for volunteers](#), and a [media kit](#). While some resources appeared in more than one section, the toolkit, resource library, and media kit were packaged for specific groups - educators/facilitators, individuals, and media. All three libraries include both internally developed resources and those created by partners.
- Internally developed resources were downloaded just over 31,000 times. The most popular resource was the Eclipse Journal in Spanish, followed by the English version of

the Eclipse Journal. Resources created for the 2023 and 2024 eclipses include (* indicates resources designed to support individual observers):

- * Updated Eclipse tool in the GLOBE Observer app. Updates for 2023 and 2024 include the addition of land cover to the site set up, improved accessibility and functionality, and updated eclipse locations and times for each path.
 - * [Landing page](#)
 - * Certificate - [English](#), [Spanish](#)
 - * How to video - [English](#), [Spanish](#)
 - * GLOBE Eclipse Intro Video (science and why participate) - [English](#), [Spanish](#)
 - * FAQs
 - Air Temperature Data Sheet - [English](#), [Spanish](#)
 - GLOBE Eclipse One-Pager (handout, poster) - [English](#), [Spanish](#)
 - GLOBE Eclipse Overview (broad how to) - [English](#), [Spanish](#)
 - How to use the GLOBE Eclipse Tool (app how to) - [English](#), [Spanish](#), [French](#)
 - [Pinhole postcard](#) (English and Spanish)
 - GLOBE Eclipse Reels (short videos) - [English](#), [Spanish](#)
 - Solar Eclipse Journal - [English](#), [Spanish](#), [French](#)
 - [Graphic assets](#) (link to download the folder) for partners or media with space for local branding
 - [GLOBE Eclipse Presentation](#)
 - [GLOBE Eclipse Tabletop Signs](#) for events
 - [Tips for Events with GLOBE Eclipse](#)
 - [Supporting GLOBE Student Investigations of the Eclipse](#)
- Partners also played a critical role in producing some products and resources.
 - The [Aerokats and Rovers Education Network \(AREN\)](#) provided instructions to develop a simple wind flag for eclipse events.
 - [NASA Eclipse Soundscapes](#) is a NASA-funded citizen science project that recruited volunteers to record changes in animal behavior and sound during the eclipse. They co-produced and co-led training events for partners, particularly for Texas Master Naturalists and libraries. GLOBE Observer posted a summary of their project on the Eclipse page and encouraged volunteers to do both projects. Eclipse Soundscapes reciprocated and encouraged their volunteers to also do GLOBE Eclipse. In particular, they integrated GLOBE Eclipse into their programming for libraries. They led a conversation in a [GO Connect event](#), which was recorded and published as a resource for partners on the Observer website. This close collaboration occurred because temperature data is highly relevant to changes in animal behavior.
 - [GLOBE Mission Earth](#) hosted joint webinars for educators and libraries with GLOBE Eclipse. GLOBE Eclipse supported a GLOBE Mission Earth-led 2024 SEES internship focused on using GLOBE Eclipse data. Both groups worked together to distribute eclipse glasses to educators. GLOBE Mission Earth also

provided Infrared (IR) thermometers and training in GLOBE surface temperature for libraries participating in GLOBE Eclipse.

- [Learning Ecosystems Northeast](#) (GMRI) provided advice in the development of the Solar Eclipse Journal, a resource created for educators and learners to take notes on their eclipse experience, which provided additional ways for engagement and learning in addition to taking observations. Educators and students can use the Solar Eclipse Journals to create Eclipse Nature Notes, a student publication produced by GMRI. Additionally, this partner co-led a workshop.
- [Navigating the Path of Totality](#) (Exploratorium) provided resources published in the Eclipse toolkit for informal educators. They also invited GLOBE Eclipse to be part of their eclipse broadcast.
- [NASA Heliophysics Education Action Team](#) (HEAT) provided general eclipse training and safety resources. They also integrated GLOBE Eclipse into their training and offered space to co-present training to internal NASA audiences.

Story from an independent partner

Mary Hartman led an eclipse program in Akron, Ohio, using resources from the GLOBE Observer website. She collected data via paper data sheets, then mailed the data with the following to GLOBE Observer:

[The event had] 45 people in attendance, age 5 yr old to age 81 yr old, on 4/8/24 to observe the Total Solar Eclipse in Bath/Akron Ohio. It was our pleasure to contribute to your data.

Partnerships for Dissemination and Engagement

The two primary partnership roles were to integrate GLOBE Eclipse into local eclipse programming and to provide support to volunteers. Collaboration included training, meeting to co-create programming, and sharing resources. Dissemination partners and the nature of the collaboration are summarized below. In this checklist, materials are physical material like thermometers or eclipse glasses. *Digital dissemination* means that partners distributed NESEC digital resources to their audiences through their website, newsletter, social media, etc.

Training to partner indicates that NESEC offered some kind of training (webinars, in-person training or collaborative conversations) directly to the partner. In some cases, NESEC presented GLOBE Eclipse to the partner organization as part of their routine programming, such as regularly scheduled Earth to Sky seminars or the GLOBE watercooler series. In other cases, such as with libraries, NESEC hosted a focused training session to which the partner was invited. These include four GLOBE Observer Connect sessions.

The final category, co-hosted training to a shared audience, means that NESEC and the partner provided at least one training session with the partner to another group. For example, NESEC and GLOBE Mission Earth co-hosted a series of educator workshops. NASA Eclipse Soundscapes and NESEC provided a co-hosted training to Texas Master Naturalists.

Table 1: Dissemination/Distribution Partnerships (see [original](#))

Partner	Materials	Digital Dissemination	Training to Partner	Co-hosted Training to a Shared Audience
NASA@MyLibrary	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
NASA Sun Spots	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The GLOBE Program	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
NASA Heliophysics Education Action Team (HEAT)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
SciStarter	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Eclipse Ambassadors	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Earth to Sky	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Museum and Informal Education Alliance	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Solar System Ambassadors	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
GLOBE Mission Earth	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
NASA Citizen Science	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
NASA Communications	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
National Informal Learning STEM Network	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Learning Ecosystems Northeast (GMRI)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
National Eclipse Ballooning Project	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
NOAA Science on a Sphere	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
American Camp Association	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
NASA Eclipse Soundscapes	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
NASA eClips	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Libraries	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Texas Master Naturalists	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Civil Air Patrol	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
STEM Enhancement in Earth Science	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
GLOBE Goes to Camp	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
HBCU Network	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Partner Distribution

Partners extended NESEC's reach for the eclipses as shown in the following maps. The top version shows the wider view to include activities in Hawaii, Alaska, and Puerto Rico. Not shown is an Eclipse Ambassador or Night Sky Network location in Guam. The lower map offers a closer view to provide differentiation along the eclipse path where there was more partner activity. Maps derived from [2024 NESEC Reach through Partnerships](#).

2024 NESEC Reach Through Partnerships

2024 NESEC Reach Through Partnerships

Story from a Distribution and Dissemination Partner: HBCU Network

Several HBCUs in and near the path of totality engaged in Eclipse events: Alcorn State University (Lorman, MS); Central State University (Wilberforce, Ohio); Harris-Stowe University (St. Louis MO); Houston-Tillotson University (Austin, TX); Philander-Smith University (Little Rock, AR) and Wiley College (Marshall, TX). Shaw University (Raleigh NC). The schools were given eclipse resources, including eclipse glasses and a webinar about eclipses and how to appropriately host a safe eclipse event. They also had access to a point of contact for eclipse questions/concerns. Their events were a blend of data collection and day of event community gatherings. The eclipse glasses helped the schools engage more people than the faculty and students collecting data.

Partner Case Studies

Not all partnerships were equal, and some involved more time or had a greater impact. The following section details five significant partnerships: Civil Air Patrol, NASA GLOBE Eclipse Libraries, Texas Master Naturalists, educators who participated in the Spring 2024 GLOBE Clouds/Eclipse Workshop for Formal & Informal Educators, and NASA SunSpots.

Civil Air Patrol

The Civil Air Patrol partnership originated with the Civil Air Patrol. Founded Dec. 1, 1941, the Civil Air Patrol is the US Air Force's Civilian Auxiliary. The roughly 36K adult and 30K youth CAP members live by their organization's motto of 'volunteers serving America's communities.' As CAP volunteers began preparations for the 2023 and 2024 solar eclipses, it became clear that the organization's unique blend of emergency services skills, youth involvement, and passion for aerospace education could be utilized to help create a valuable data set.

To that end, on June 12, 2023, Captain Shannon Babb reached out through the GLOBE Observer help desk email asking for information to engage about 200 cadets in collecting data during the October annular eclipse. As a volunteer with the Civil Air Patrol (CAP), Captain Babb was organizing an eclipse mission to train cadets, ages 12-20, in the western United States to collect data during the eclipse. She wanted to include GLOBE Eclipse temperature and clouds in the mission along with observations of animal behavior through NASA Eclipse Soundscapes and changes in VHF radio operations. We agreed that having the cadets participate would be welcome and sent her the previously developed training slides and the URL to the eclipse page with information about data collection.

Cpt. Babb and a team of volunteers integrated GLOBE Eclipse into the CAP Eclipse Mission based on the materials we sent. Under the mission, teams of cadets trained together to collect data during the October eclipse. CAP held a mission patch design contest, and a 13-year-old in Colorado submitted the winning design, shown below. The patches were printed and distributed to participating teams.

On October 14, 2023, 191 teams of cadets (about 1,650 individuals) in 35 states and Puerto Rico collected air temperature, clouds, and wind speed and direction data during the eclipse and submitted it through the GLOBE Observer app and paper data sheets.

Civil Air Patrol October Lessons Learned

During the annular eclipse, a few teams experienced problems with the app, which was resolved by recording the observations on paper. 152 observations came in through the paper data sheets.

The app problems fell into three categories: inexperience, issues with photo collection, and data connectivity issues. The issue with photos was that cadets had the phone screen locked, so rotating the phone to landscape wouldn't launch the photo collection portion of the clouds tool. Both the photo issue and inexperience could be resolved with training and practice. Connectivity issues are known to arise during large events like an eclipse. The app is designed to work offline so that users can save and submit data later. We advised CAP teams to use the app offline and submit data later during the April eclipse.

The second lesson was that we couldn't track the amount of data submitted through the CAP partnership during the October eclipse. CAP did not implement a single GLOBE team for the annular eclipse, so it's not possible to ascertain how much data they submitted overall.

However, 32 squadrons set up a GLOBE team, and through that we can identify that 362 air temperature observations, 11 land cover observations, and 115 clouds observations were submitted by individuals on these teams.

The final take away from the October eclipse was that cadets who participated really enjoyed the experience. Cpt. Babb called it a transformative experience. Two of the teams had such a positive experience, they raised funds to travel to totality for April 2024.

Civil Air Patrol Preparation for April Eclipse

Taking these lessons forward, Cpt. Babb and her team created [paper data sheets](#) for the 2024 total solar eclipse. She also created a national [GLOBE Team](#) to track the data submitted as part of the Civil Air Patrol mission.

CAP also created a new opportunity to build on the excitement reported from the October eclipse. Captain Babb reported:

Several cadets who participated in the October eclipse wanted to find a way to share their enthusiasm for solar eclipses, so we launched a [CAP Solar Eclipse Classroom](#) program. In addition to encouraging educators to participate in the GLOBE Observer Eclipse project, CAP Solar Eclipse Classrooms can request cadets to come in and provide lessons about weather and eclipses.

The Solar Eclipse Classroom material provided educators a way to teach the eclipse and collect data aligned to grade-level standards. It included activities, background information, data collection sheets and the opportunity to request a presentation from a local cadet. More than 200 education sites, including schools, libraries, museums, and after school groups, signed up to become CAP Solar Eclipse Classrooms. In the two weeks leading up to the April total eclipse, cadets gave presentations about solar eclipse science in approximately 400 classrooms, providing peer-to-peer learning. Additional classrooms attended virtual presentations.

As a result of the CAP Solar Eclipse Classroom, just over 41,500 K-12 students (600 educators) collected GLOBE eclipse data. Just over 21 percent of the participating teachers said this was the first time their students had collected real world data. Almost all of the data collected was tracked solely on paper data sheets and was not submitted to GLOBE. CAP is working to upload at least some of the data from these schools.

CAP Participation During the April 2024 Total Solar Eclipse

On April 8, approximately 4,000 Civil Air Patrol members nationwide worked together in teams of 5-15 to collect air temperature, clouds, wind speed/direction, and precipitation data in all 50 states, District of Columbia, Puerto Rico, and two Canadian provinces. This made the solar eclipse the largest one-day mission in Civil Air Patrol history. Participants ranged in age from 12 to 93.

The national GLOBE Team for Civil Air Patrol, the CAP Solar Eclipse Mission, had 673 members. They submitted 6,313 total observations in the week leading up to the eclipse and on April 8, 2024. Significantly, they provided data off the path of totality, where participation among other types of volunteers was more scarce. This partnership accounts for approximately 70 percent of the cloud data received during the eclipse. Data submitted is detailed in the data section.

Distribution of CAP team observations:

Civil Air Patrol data collected by teams and in classrooms on paper is outstanding. They are formatting the data for email data entry and should be submitted by the end of 2024. This includes 42,982 data points as follows:

- 10,420 air temperature observations
- 10,569 wind measurements
- 5,842 precipitation measurements
- 16,151 clouds

Impact on Cadets and Future Plans

Collecting solar eclipse data for the GLOBE Observer Project as part of the CAP Solar Eclipse Mission was a life-changing experience for many CAP volunteers. 78% of surveyed Civil Air Patrol members indicated that participating in the Solar Eclipse Mission increased their interest in Weather and Astronomy, with just over 10% of surveyed cadets indicating that this experience made them consider a career in meteorology, astronomy, or space weather for the first time.

Post event surveys showed that the largest driving factor for cadet participation in the solar eclipse mission was the desire to be involved with something larger than themselves. Many surveyed CAP members indicated that Mission design helped foster a feeling of connectedness because they could participate across all time zones, in rural and urban communities, and in their native language. Approximately 10 percent of CAP solar eclipse teams were Spanish speaking. These cadets said that being able to participate in Spanish helped them understand the content better and increased engagement and excitement. Interest in meteorology careers rose most in the Spanish-speaking cadets.

Both GLOBE and the Civil Air Patrol are eager to continue this partnership. Discussions are underway to continue the collaboration. Ideas include a CAP weather classroom and a new CAP mission, possibly around clouds and contrails. Additionally, activity in the national CAP GLOBE team shows that a few CAP volunteers are continuing to collect GLOBE Clouds data on their own, indicating that this partnership succeeded in generating some ongoing engagement.

GLOBE Eclipse Libraries

Beginning in spring 2023, NESEC, NASA@ My Library, and GLOBE Mission Earth partnered to recruit, select, and support [GLOBE Eclipse Libraries](#) - a group of 100 U.S. public libraries that committed to offering eclipse programming to engage their communities in GLOBE. Libraries were selected from 188 applications with the goal of engaging a diverse group of libraries based on geography, communities and audiences served, and types of programming offered.

This collaboration leveraged each partner's unique capabilities and resources:

NESEC identified and provided resources that would best support library programming. Each of the physical kits included: bi-lingual promotional cards (100 pack), GLOBE Sky Window activity and field guide (100 packs of English and Spanish), Elementary GLOBE Do You Know that Clouds Have Names books (10 packs of English and Spanish), and Taylor air temperature thermometers (1). NESEC also hosted webinars, office hours, and an online BaseCamp to foster a community of practice.

NAML advised NESEC on library kit content, promoted the opportunity through the STARnet library network and eclipse programs: e-newsletters, workshops during spring and summer 2023, and hosted a May 2023 informational webinar for over 200 libraries with NESEC and GME. NAML also handled central distribution of the GLOBE Eclipse Library Kits.

Through a separate competitive application process, NAML selected an additional 49 libraries nationwide in geographic areas with large Spanish-speaking populations, to receive bilingual (Spanish/English) solar science kits in September 2023 that included the GLOBE Eclipse kits (resources and air temperature thermometers) and Eclipse Soundscapes AudioMoths recording devices. NAML, Eclipse Soundscapes, and NESEC collaborated on two webinars with libraries that received the bilingual solar science kits: 1) September 7 "unboxing" webinar and 2) September 27 deeper dive into Eclipse Soundscapes and GLOBE Eclipse kit resources.

GME, with NESEC, selected a subset of GLOBE Eclipse Libraries (25) to receive infrared thermometers (IRTs) to also take surface temperature observations. GME provided GLOBE surface temperature training and ongoing support, and participated in GLOBE Eclipse Library webinars, office hours, and BaseCamp.

Below: Map showing library locations receiving GLOBE-related eclipse resources

Preparing and Training Libraries for the Eclipses

Webinars and Office Hours

Libraries received physical GLOBE Eclipse Kits in July and from August 2023 to April 2024, NESEC hosted a series of seven professional development webinars, four office hours, and co-presented on three STARnet Libraries webinars. Libraries were also invited to, and many attended, GLOBE Observer Connect webinars.

GLOBE Eclipse Libraries were required to attend at least one professional development webinar, with many attending multiple webinars and sharing webinar links with their staff. The live webinars were well-attended (ranging from 40 to over 200), with many participants reporting they could not attend the live event, but planned to watch recordings. Viewing statistics show that many did indeed watch the recordings (e.g., Views of webinar recordings for December-73 views, January-106 and February-70).

Webinar topics were selected with input from libraries, with several library staff co-presenting. Following is a list of webinars and topics covered.

[Citizen Science and Library Eclipse Programming: GLOBE Observer \(May 4, 2023\)](#)

STARNet Libraries Webinar on Eclipse Citizen Science, which included an overview of GLOBE Eclipse and Clouds, Library Resources, and going further by taking surface temperature with an infrared thermometer.

[GLOBE Eclipse Libraries Webinar \(Aug. 16, 2023\)](#) Topics: Eclipse Safety, GLOBE Eclipse tool, finding local Subject Matter Experts, additional resources for libraries.

[GLOBE Eclipse Libraries Webinar \(Sept. 13, 2023\)](#)

Topics: Presentations by Oldham Public Library and North Little Rock Public Library; walk-through of the GLOBE Eclipse app in staging, overview of promotional resources available to use/adapt, and walkthrough of the Taylor 1441E air temperature thermometer.

[Two for One: GLOBE Eclipse and Eclipse Soundscapes \(December 6, 2023\)](#)

Discussion with GLOBE Clouds and Eclipse Soundscapes scientists who talked about why they are excited library sites will take observations of both atmospheric conditions and animal behavior, and why these co-located observations will make a unique contribution to science. Discussion of strategies related to common challenges (e.g., weather and logistics of large public events).

[GLOBE Eclipse Libraries Webinar: Planning and Timeline for the April 8 Eclipse \(January 10, 2024\)](#) Topics: tips/advice from libraries for eclipse programs; Quick Recaps and Summary from October eclipse; Nominal planning timeline; and Program Planning template.

GLOBE Eclipse Library Webinar: [Library Programs and New Resources \(Feb 22, 2024\)](#)

Topics: Programs and plans by: 1) Stewart C. Meyer Public Library, Texas 2) Starkville-Oktibbeha County Public Library System, Mississippi 3) New Brunswick Free Public Library, NJ and 4) Macedon Public Library, NY and New GLOBE Eclipse resources.

GLOBE Eclipse Library Webinar: [Refresher/Walk-through GLOBE Eclipse \(March 14, 2024\)](#)

Topics: Walk through GLOBE Eclipse tool, new resources (table top signs, data collection sheet, etc), and how to promote events through SciStarter and the National Space Council's Find Your Place in Space initiative.

[Final Webinar and Celebration](#) - Libraries and Texas Master Naturalists (April 23, 2024)
Participants shared their eclipse stories In this celebration

Promoting a Library Community of Practice

BaseCamp is an online project management and collaboration platform used by the NESEC team. In August 2023, NESEC created a GLOBE Eclipse Libraries BaseCamp project that was open to all participating library staff with the objective of fostering a community of practice. Library staff were first introduced to the BaseCamp at the August 21 office hour, with refreshers at subsequent webinars and office hours.

The BaseCamp project was reorganized after the October eclipse based on feedback and responses by library staff to a NESEC survey (OSU, 2023). As a result, an expanded “Resources for Programs” section was organized around seven categories: 1) Activities 2) FAQs, Tips and Tricks, and Background Info 3) Livestreams from totality (a popular library program for a rainy eclipse day); 4) Observing; 5) Printables; 6) Promotion/Media Resources; and 7) Webinar Recordings/Notes.

Below: Screenshot of the “Resources for Programs” section of the libraries BaseCamp

Ongoing Library Engagement and Support

The library BaseCamp was an active online space with over 216 Campfire posts and 21 Discussion Threads from July 2023 to April 2024, with interactions peaking during the two months leading up to each eclipse (September-October and March-April).

Examples of the kinds of interactions between libraries and with the NESEC team included sharing ideas and resources; describing library programs; asking questions; reporting problems, troubleshooting technical issues, announcing related events, commiserating about a rainy eclipse day, and celebrating successes of programs that went well.

There were also steady email exchanges with library staff who reached out directly for support. These required varying levels of engagement and time, from simple (e.g., "I missed a webinar was it recorded?") to more complicated requests requiring back-and-forth exchanges (e.g., help finding a local subject matter expert, science questions requiring additional consultations to answer, and troubleshooting technical issues).

These interactions were also valuable for surfacing unknown issues. For example, GLOBE Educator accounts registered as informal educators were not able to set up student accounts, which was crucial for several participating libraries (e.g., one librarian was running an afterschool club with a local elementary school and needed to set up student accounts for participating children). Once alerted to the problem, the GLOBE DIS team was able to fix this.

When questions were answered - whether on BaseCamp, via email, or at webinars - responses were added to the GLOBE Eclipse Libraries FAQ (a frequently updated [Google doc](#)) and also posted in the BaseCamp chat so that everyone had the same information.

NASA GLOBE Eclipse Library Programming

For the October 14 annular eclipse, libraries reported offering more than 100 programs for 7,206 participants. For the April 8 solar eclipse, libraries offered more than 350 programs for more than 32,500 participants. The graph below shows the type of library programs offered for the April 8 eclipse, which included a wide range of audiences: children, families, youth, schools and homeschools, adults, and seniors.

Above: Library partners reported that for the 2023 annular eclipse they conducted 159 different GLOBE Observer-related eclipse programs reaching ~7K participants. For the 2024 total eclipse, they conducted 350 different GLOBE Observer-related eclipse programs reaching ~32.5K participants leading up to or on the April 8 total solar eclipse. Source: Oregon State University 2023 and 2024 evaluation report.

For example, one librarian partnered with a local elementary school to offer a weekly science club, that she named “Sky Watchers.” “I told them when they were taking observations, if anyone asked them what they were doing to say, ‘I am a Citizen Scientist and I work for NASA. I am collecting weather data.’ One little boy really got excited about that and I heard him tell his mom he was working for NASA as they were leaving. I forwarded the NASA satellite response to the after school coordinator with a note from me and she read it to them yesterday afternoon. That really excited them because it was evidence this is the real deal. I plan to send them notes and encouragement until our next meeting.”

Above: Locations of library programs and number of participants reached for the 2023 annular eclipse and 2024 total solar eclipse. Source: Oregon State University 2023 and 2024 evaluation report.

People who joined a GLOBE Team associated with a library submitted 1,593 air temperature observations, 39 land cover observations, and 394 clouds observations. Additional data may have come from this partnership outside of the GLOBE teams. We also see data coming from these teams after the eclipse, indicating ongoing engagement (see below).

Ongoing Library Engagement

As part of their engagement in GLOBE Eclipse, librarians also learned about other ways to engage in GLOBE through GLOBE Observer. Ninety percent of Eclipse Librarians reported moderate to high interest in continuing to work with the GLOBE Observer app and team in providing learning experiences for their communities. The GLOBE Eclipse Libraries team does show that some individuals have continued to submit GLOBE data after the eclipse. Librarians are also part of the broader STARnet community, through which they will receive ongoing opportunities to engage with NASA.

[GLOBE Eclipse Library Team Page](#) shows ongoing data collection. High numbers of air temperature and barometric pressure data points indicate that one or more members of the team has a weather station reporting data.

Stories from Library Partners

Southfield Public Library, Michigan (near Detroit) ([70+ photos on their Facebook Post](#))
Our eclipse event turned out great - a sunny warm day that drew 3,000 people to get eclipse glasses and 1,000 staying for our watch party. Based on items you shared we had color sheets, information sheets, did the cloud in a bottle experiment, were confident in our temperature taking abilities and to share that knowledge with our community.

Texas Master Naturalists

The [Texas Master Naturalist](#) (TMN) Program is funded by Texas AgriLife Extension Service and Texas Parks and Wildlife Service to develop a community of volunteers dedicated to managing natural resources and natural areas. As Texas experienced both the October and April eclipses, this organization was a natural partner to seek out as we looked for potential ambassadors for GLOBE Eclipse.

In May 2023, NESEC attended the TMN volunteer fair to offer GLOBE Eclipse as a volunteer opportunity for the coming year. With NASA Eclipse Soundscapes, we co-presented at a state-wide training webinar in June 2023. We provided an additional 3 webinars prior to the annular eclipse.

TMN held their statewide in-person conference in October 2023 to coincide with the eclipse. Dorian Janney attended representing NESEC and gave an in-person presentation about the annular eclipse, and then experienced the eclipse with the 600 attendees. Later in October, we held a virtual follow up meeting to share experiences and lessons learned in preparation for April's total eclipse.

At the end of January, we held a second kick-off webinar for the total eclipse. From that, 90 volunteers joined an Eclipse Educators group to get support and share ideas around the total solar eclipse. The group collaborated via a Basecamp board, much as the libraries did. Science information and resources were organized in a StoryMap as a sort of online textbook, something the TMN volunteers found to be extremely valuable. Additionally, Dorian held a bi-weekly office hour to answer questions and sent out a biweekly email. These bi-weekly contacts served to build relationships and maintain a connection with the TMN volunteers.

In a post-eclipse survey, 6 volunteers reported holding events, reaching an estimated 1,000 people. However, more TMN volunteers reported events informally via email and Basecamp. As many as 90 events, ranging from small book club conversations to Rotary Club presentations, were reported informally. Several presentations or events were held with homeschool groups, cub scouts, or family events. One TMN volunteer led 11 events ranging from a family reunion to formal events associated with Earth Science Week, reaching 1,290 people.

TMN activities were largely local, community level events reaching out through organizations like city parks or scouts or church groups. Some were on eclipse day, both October and April, but events started immediately following the June 2023 training. All together events reported informally reached 3,400 people.

Data collected through the GLOBE Team set up for Texas Master Naturalists is likely not a full

reflection of activity. The team submitted 521 air temperature observations, 11 land cover observations, and 124 clouds observations. Because TMN volunteers were individuals or small groups, they may not have joined the team for data collection.

Texas Master Naturalists Lessons Learned

Many of the TMN volunteers weren't interested in engaging in data collection through the GLOBE Observer app largely because they felt they already knew what would happen. They didn't feel that it was an important observation to make scientifically. When they experienced the October annular eclipse, they realized that the data collection was a good opportunity for public engagement. One said: We "took measurements using the app during the eclipse. That enhanced the experience for everyone." Another said: "Your suggestions and data collection projects made this event so much more...well, more everything — meaningful, fun, enjoyable!"

This group used the Basecamp as a repository for information, but didn't interact in the space. Based on post-event conversations, they enjoyed training webinars, but not the conversation time. Drop in office hours weren't well attended. They want to continue learning and seemed to be more comfortable with the lecture format.

The real impact of the TMN partnership is not the data collected through this group. It is the local, community-scale conversations about eclipses that occurred as a result of the partnership. Volunteers brought GLOBE Eclipse into their families, to friends and church, on hikes and to small out of school groups. Generating conversation at this level is extremely difficult for a project managed from the top down to achieve. The partnership gave us an influential friend in local communities, and that is powerful.

Stories from Texas Master Naturalist Volunteers

Heidi Barr writes:

I led a watch party of 50+ people at the Lewisville Lake Environmental Learning Area (LLELA) on April 8. We had several activities:

- Art station where folks could create their names in lights, by poking holes in card stock and allowing sunlight to pass through to shine mini eclipses on the ground
- Shadow station- various items placed on a table with a long piece of paper so they could trace the shadow and note the time. (Sun dial)
- Science station- several thermometers (ground, table top and tree branches) to note the temp differences throughout the eclipse event. There was an eclipse model to show the position of the celestial bodies. Lemon and regular Oreos to allow folks to create their own eclipse and enjoy a treat.
- A Solar balloon- black plastic tube tethered at the ends. When hot, the balloon rose, during totality, it dropped like a stone!
- Telescope station. A telescope with an approved filter was on hand for viewing the eclipse. People were great at taking turns!
- Hikes- we had several MN on hand to lead hikes through the woods (scatter patterns). That group observed wildlife at a nearby pond- birds going to roost, frogs and crickets starting to sing, even an owl swooped in!
- Participants also had a booklet to record their experiences, including black stickers to cover the sun at 5 different times

The event was limited to 50 and filled up in the span of about 2 days!

Mary C. Lott shared:

Our sun & moon watchers came from the UK, CA, AL, FL and NY. Besides Cooper's BBQ with all the fixin's we had HEB bake an Eclipse cake. Solar eclipses happened repeatedly with Oreo cookie demonstrations. As the eclipse progressed, there was a lot of whooping and hollering every time the clouds opened to give us a peek. At totality, the veil of cloud cover made the corona look like brilliant whips of light. Then the wind picked up, the temperature dropped, & the birds started singing and became more active. The children (3-5) were thrilled. We toasted the sun's return with shots of Sunkist orange and played a version of Eclipse Bingo that Dorian shared with us at the Annual Meeting in McAllen last fall. Mini banana and chocolate moon pies

were the coveted prizes. All the while we had my Eclipse playlist playing in the background. Dorian, I appreciate you and all for your guidance. Your suggestions and data collection projects made this event so much more...well, more everything — meaningful, fun, enjoyable..... Young and old, family and friends went away happy and warmed by our time spent together for this spectacular show. Thank you.

Texas Master Naturalists Future Engagement

Going forward, we will continue to invite TMN volunteers to learning events such as campaign webinars and GLOBE Observer Connect events. TMN volunteers were invited to the Global Precipitation Measurement Mission webinar series, which they attended throughout 2024. Thirty to forty percent of US attendees at the webinars have been TMN volunteers.

We will also engage them when there is a real science issue that they can support via in-app data requests. They are active volunteers who want to engage and learn, but are also careful to choose volunteer activities that have real meaning to them.

Spring 2024 GLOBE Clouds/Eclipse Workshop for Formal & Informal Educators

As part of NESEC and GLOBE Mission Earth, the GLOBE Clouds team at NASA Langley Research Center reached just over 60 educators through a [five session workshop](#) in March and April 2024. Educators were trained on GLOBE Clouds, GLOBE Air Temperature, Eclipses and GLOBE Eclipse Tool, GLOBE Surface Temperature, and on how to complete a research project.

Participants received two templates; the first helped them collect and graph air temperature, cloud cover, and surface temperature before and after the eclipse; the second walked educators through the creation of research posters to document their findings related to atmospheric changes they observed in their locations. Thirteen educators—representing the states of Louisiana, New Hampshire, New Jersey, Ohio, Rhode Island, South Carolina, Tennessee, Texas, and Vermont—published their research posters on the GLOBE Mission Earth Student Research webpage.

Educators joined a GLOBE team, [Eclipse Workshop 2024](#). Between April 6 and April 9, educators in the team submitted 2,480 data points, including 957 air temperature observations and 335 clouds observations. These educators also submitted data from protocols not included in GLOBE Eclipse, but that are relevant to atmospheric change during an eclipse such as barometric pressure, relative humidity, and winds. This indicates deeper engagement in GLOBE. Many of the educators submitted data after April 8, indicating an ongoing engagement in GLOBE.

The GLOBE Team associated with the workshop series collected 655 air temperature observations, 19 land cover observations, and 316 clouds observations during the April total solar eclipse.

Story from an Educator

Lisa Valle, an educator from Tonawanda, NY, said:

My kids were really excited about the eclipse! They all mentioned how cold it got during totality!! It fit in perfectly because I'm teaching them Weather right now. We also have done a couple of Globe surface and cloud readings. My students really enjoy this kind of stuff!

We made surface temperature and cloud cover readings Friday! The kids ask to go out and do them. They get so excited when I show them their matched readings. Thank you so much for have a program that my kids feel like they are a part of NASA.

I am not sure if I already told you, I am a recipient of a Moon Tree!! [Being] a part of GLOBE was a contributing factor of my application. It's going into the ground tomorrow morning.

Thanks for the certificates. I will be handing those out during our end of the year awards ceremony.

GLOBE Community Engagement

The NESEC team held 13 GLOBE Eclipse Community Conversations approximately monthly from January 2023 through April 2024. The purpose of these sessions was to share information about eclipse events happening within the GLOBE community, and to share resources across groups. A total of 45 different GLOBE educators or partners participated in the sessions, although the consistent group was about 20-25 participants. [Notes from all of the sessions](#) were also made available for reference later. The group also provided useful feedback for improvements for processes and materials between the annular eclipse in October and the total eclipse in April.

Prior to the initial convening of the GLOBE Eclipse Community Conversations, NESEC team members presented at the U.S. GLOBE Watercooler on December 1, 2022, especially to share data collection options and to brainstorm ideas on how to conduct investigations around both eclipses. The NASA Langley team presented about My NASA Data eclipse activities on September 13, 2023. An additional session focused on the April total solar eclipse was held on March 6, 2024, focusing on how to use the GLOBE Eclipse tool as well as supplemental resources and materials available to support events during the upcoming eclipse.

The GSFC GLOBE Observer team distributed approximately 4000 eclipse glasses from the NASA HQ eclipse team to members of the GLOBE community, primarily before the annular eclipse in October. Locations of the events supported by the distribution included the University of Toledo, the University of Tennessee at Chattanooga, an outdoor campus of the Osher Lifelong Learning Institute in South Dakota, the Perdue University College of Science, El Paso Community College, the Gene Roddenberry Planetarium/El Paso Independent School District, and to the GLOBE Latin America and Caribbean Regional Office/Universidad Austral, Argentina.

The LaRC GLOBE Clouds team spearheaded a much larger eclipse glasses distribution of 20,000 units before the April eclipse. Those glasses were distributed directly to GLOBE teachers in batches of 50 or 100, and were sent to approximately 220 sites around the United States.

NASA SunSpots

The NESEC team supported three large-scale, NASA-sponsored events in October and April during the eclipses. However, by partnering with NASA broadly, we were able to extend our reach significantly. We participated in the Albuquerque, NM, NASA SunSpot in October, trying a number of possible tabling activities during the International Balloon Fiesta, at which NASA exhibited for 4 days. Materials were also sent to support an event in Boulder, Colorado for the annular eclipse, staffed by GIO UCAR personnel.

Based on that experience, we assembled an event kit, a blog, and a training for SunSpot event organizers in preparation for April.

The event kit included various items for tabling in both English and Spanish, including signs saying GLOBE Eclipse, laminated GLOBE Eclipse one-pagers, cloud charts, and tabletop signs with QR codes. For the April eclipse, laminated versions of materials produced later, such as the GLOBE Eclipse overview and how-to flier, were also included, as were examples of paper data collection sheets and the Solar Eclipse Journal. French versions of the resources available in that language were provided to the Niagara Falls SunSpot. Unless the site already had them on hand, most kits also included thermometers, both a liquid-filled simple calibration thermometer and a digital thermometer.

For locations that did not receive a kit, we provided a digital kit in the form of a [blog](#) post. The blog highlighted lessons learned during the October eclipse, including links to printable tabling signs, activities that work well to communicate the Sun-Earth connection during a large event and tips about how to manage challenges related to large events. Activities suggestions include eclipse viewing tips, tracking temperature on a temperature chart, cloud in a bottle, and solar eclipse journal.

We offered brief training to approximately 20 SunSpot organizers during their regular coordination meetings, and we sent eclipse event kits to six locations. These locations provided large-scale events, reaching more than a million people combined. We know the materials were deployed at the following locations: Kerrville, Dallas, Austin (Texas), Indianapolis, Wallops, GSFC Visitor Center (Greenbelt), North Carolina arboretum, Hot Springs (Arkansas), and

Niagara Falls. NESEC team members directly supported the events in Dallas, North Carolina, Austin, and Wallops. While this engagement was shallow, it did provide a touch point for many who would not have engaged via data collection.

NESEC-produced GLOBE Observer activity and materials at the NASA SunSpot exhibit in Kerrville, Texas. No NESEC team members supported the event, so this is fully partner driven.

The NASA SunSpot events in Dallas were directly supported by the NESEC team, though other staff also used NESEC Eclipse resources.

Because of the nature of large events, we did not set up a GLOBE team or encourage people to engage via a team. We were interested in new individuals downloading and using the app. The primary desired outcome was awareness of the Sun-Earth connection by getting people to notice changes in temperature and clouds.

Story from NASA SunSpot Partners

I was part of the NASA eclipse team in Hot Springs National Park. We used the GLOBE thermometers to track the temperature during the eclipse at 15 minute intervals and posted it on a big graph. We had a booth, and people who were at the booth during that time would read off the thermometer and we would mark the temperature on the graph. People were fascinated by this process, and wanted to see the data after the eclipse was finished. Several came back to take a picture of the graph or one with them posing with it.

I wanted to share this experience and the pictures with you. It was definitely a crowd pleaser. (While I had verbal confirmation from everyone in these pictures to share them, you may want to keep them in-house, especially the ones with children.) Thanks for allowing deeper science connections with park visitors.

best wishes,

*Theresa J. Summer (she/her/hers)
Astronomy Educator / Diversity Coordinator
Astronomical Society of the Pacific*

NASA Wallops Flight Facility Event

Brian Campbell said: During the 2024 Solar Eclipse and the Atmospheric Perturbations around Eclipse Path (APEP) Rocket Launch Event at the NASA Wallops Flight Facility in Wallops Island, Virginia, I set up a GLOBE Observer Eclipse table where participants assisted in taking air temperature before, during and after the eclipse. We reached 84.4% totality in this location, but we actually had a 19F temperature drop.

National Aeronautics and Space Administration

NASA WALLOPS VISITOR CENTER

SOLAR ECLIPSE & MULTI-ROCKET LAUNCH VIEWING EVENT

04. 08. 24
1-5 P.M. EDT

Eclipse glasses for safe viewing, live streaming, resources and solar-themed activities available

FROM WALLOPS LOCATION:
81.4 % PARTIAL ECLIPSE VISIBLE
Start of partial eclipse: 2:06 p.m.
Maximum eclipse: 3:22 p.m.
End of partial eclipse: 4:33 p.m.

3 Black Brant IX Sounding Rockets to launch between 2:40-4:05 p.m. with approximately 45 minutes between each rocket for the APEP-2 Mission

2024

Please enjoy the eclipse safely.
For full details call 757-824-1404 or visit www.facebook.com/nasawfvisitorcenter
All programs are subject to change or cancellation due to launch operations and exhibit renovations space and supplies limited.
www.nasa.gov www.nasa.gov/centers/wallops/visitorcenter

Time	Temp (F)	Humidity (%)	Wind Speed (mph)	Wind Dir (deg)	Clouds (%)
13:06	70.4	4.8	12.2	175	5
13:36	69.1	6.7	15.2	58.8	6.1
13:56	68.5	5.7	15.2	56.8	6.8
13:56	67.8	7.2	15.4	57.8	5.6
13:56	67.8	7.2	15.4	57.8	5.6
13:56	67.8	7.2	15.4	57.8	5.6
14:06	74.0	6.2	16.1	62.2	5.0
14:16	74.0	3.6	16.2	71.8	4.3
14:26	70.0	3.6	16.3	77.7	11.5
14:36	73.6	3.8			
14:46	72.8	5.1			
14:56	67.6	9.4			
15:06	59.1	6.7			
15:16	57.4	6.9			

Public Observation

SciStarter

As a SciStarter affiliate, users can connect the GLOBE Observer app to their SciStarter dashboard, allowing data collected via the app to show along with data contributed to other citizen science projects. During the period August 1, 2023 through April 30, 2024, 585 people added GLOBE Observer: Clouds to their dashboard. Since the GLOBE Observer: Clouds page was created on SciStarter in July of 2018 through September 2024, a total of 4743 users have joined the project there, and there have been 2095 views and 1818 saves of the project page.

The GLOBE Observer: Eclipse page has 90 joins, 2324 views, and 56 saves in the same timeframe.

In addition to the perennial pages for each of the four tools, events were created in SciStarter to try to attract additional users. Specific events were created for the GLOBE Observer Connect on October 5, 2023, about Eclipse 2023 (367 pageviews), GLOBE Eclipse Data Collection on April 8, 2024 (225 pageviews, 4 saves), and the GLOBE Eclipse Challenge from March 15 to April 15, 2024 (225 pageviews, 5 saves).

Note: As a result of an iOS update in March of 2024, it is not possible to make the connection to a SciStarter account on the latest iOS versions. The option is still available on the settings page in the GLOBE Observer app for iPhones running previous versions of iOS and on Android phones. This means that during some of the peak eclipse period, new users with iPhones were not able to add GLOBE Observer to their SciStarter dashboard, which likely resulted in lower numbers in the stats above compared to what we might have gotten if the connection were working correctly. The issue has since been resolved.

Direct Approach to Recruiting and Supporting Volunteers

The NESEC team reached potential volunteers directly through presentations, events, web articles and content, social media and traditional media. The engagements in the table below represent a one-time contact with the audience rather than sustained relationship building. While media professionals are not necessarily volunteers reached directly, the interactions with these individuals was minimal rather than longer term relationship building. Therefore, media is included here rather than with partner-mediated reach.

Direct Audiences	Engagement	Total Engaged (if known)
Students	17 presentations to students	1422
Existing volunteers	2 Email updates, 4 GO Connect sessions, 3 blogs/web articles	516 (GO Connect)
Life Long Learners	4 two hour courses, 1 Osher Lifelong Learning Institute presentation	28
Public - Events	10 events (both day of and before), 2 presentations	~6,000*
Public - Social Media	NASA social story (IG, Snapchat), 7 GLOBE social videos, regular GLOBE social posts	2.2 million+ (direct reach only, not including shares)

Scientists	9 presentations, 1 conference booth	1690
Media	48 news stories, media kit (1000 views), 7 articles on NASA sites	1048 (media professionals, not their reach)
Decision makers	1 presentation	

*Reach does not include NASA SunSpot events, which were covered under partnerships.

Events

The NESEC team supported 10 in-person events on both the day of and before the eclipses. Events ranged from live and virtual presentations, such as a public NASA Engage Session co-hosted with NASA HEAT, to pre-eclipse tabling activities at both large and small events. These do not include formal NASA SunSpot events, which are counted separately as a partner event.

Communication products

To bring new volunteers to GLOBE and to reach the existing volunteer base, NESEC initiated a four-prong eclipse communication strategy:

- We invited global participation in eclipse and clouds observations by hosting a [GLOBE Eclipse Challenge](#): Clouds and Our Solar-Powered Earth in the month around the eclipse (March 15 - April 15).
- To promote the challenge and the eclipse, we created a series of social media products released on both GLOBE and NASA platforms
- We wrote news items and coordinated with NASA communications in the production of NASA web and newsletter products
- We provided interviews and resources to the media.
- We maintained the GLOBE Observer website with an eclipse landing page and toolkit with all digital resources.

These efforts resulted in 114 communication products, many of which did not originate with the NESEC team.

GLOBE Eclipse Challenge: Clouds on Our Solar-Powered Earth and Social Media

The [GLOBE Eclipse Challenge](#) invited volunteers worldwide to observe clouds in changing conditions, such as different times of the day or when weather systems shift. Between March 15 and April 15, volunteers from over 90 countries collected more than 23,000 GLOBE Clouds observations, generating 25,444 satellite matches.

Social Media

Challenge and associated eclipse communication centered on a social media campaign that set a steady beat with regular releases meant to raise awareness and create conversation starting a little over a month before the April 8 eclipse and running through the end of April. Overall, known social media reach was nearly 2.2 million, not including any reach obtained from shares. The largest known reach came from a short image series about the challenge released on the NASA flagship Instagram, Facebook, and Snapchat accounts on March 15, reaching over 1.75 million people.

The GLOBE Observer team created 7 short videos in English and Spanish, released between March 13 and April 23 on the GLOBE Facebook and Instagram pages and reels and stories and published in horizontal format on YouTube as shorts. These were shared on NASA Earth, NASA Climate, NASA Langley, and NASA Espanol Facebook and Instagram accounts. NASA Earth and Do NASA Science independently posted about GLOBE Eclipse on X, and GLOBE Eclipse was featured in a NASA Science Live on the NASA Flagship Facebook account. The Exploratorium included GLOBE Eclipse in a YouTube video. Others also posted about GLOBE Eclipse on various social media channels, including NASA Earth Data, NASA Wallops, Joint Polar Satellite System (JPSS), AGU (Tumblr post), Civil Air Patrol, and a news meteorologist (Jeremy Lewan). Finally individuals at companies associated with the team posted about GLOBE Eclipse on LinkedIn.

NASA News and Newsletter Products

The GLOBE Observer team supplied blog posts to [NASA Shadow Notes](#) on science.nasa.gov and to [NASA's Earth Observatory](#). We posted a blog to the GLOBE website about [how students can do eclipse research with GLOBE](#) and a news article to the GLOBE Observer website about [how to use GLOBE resources in an eclipse event](#).

The team also supported the production of additional NASA news articles and events by providing material or information. Two articles on science.nasa.gov included GLOBE Eclipse: [Contribute to NASA Research on Eclipse Day and Every Day](#) and [Citizen scientists invited to](#)

[collect data for NASA during eclipse](#). The Earth Observatory published two images of the day that included GLOBE Eclipse ([The best places to view the eclipse](#) and [Cloudy with a chance of eclipse](#)), and JPL mentioned GLOBE Eclipse in [The Science of Solar Eclipses](#). GLOBE was mentioned in [NASA's live eclipse broadcast](#) and listed as an [eclipse opportunity on the NASA website](#).

The GLOBE Clouds team promoted the challenge and the associated cloud science in their [spring newsletter](#), which is posted on the GLOBE website and emailed to cloud volunteers and educators. The challenge and GLOBE eclipse were also promoted in the [NASA Express newsletter](#) to educators, which is sent to just over a million educators.

News

Several members of the NESEC team provided media interviews (at least 21 interviews) leading up to, during and after the eclipse. We identified 48 news stories or broadcasts that included GLOBE Eclipse. The full list, including URLs, is [here](#).

To simplify the process of providing resources to reporters, we created an [eclipse media kit](#). The kit included talking points, sample social media posts, basic graphic assets, diagrams showing how to participate in GLOBE Eclipse, videos, b-roll, and printable resources like our postcard. The kit received just over 1,100 views from its creation in March through May 8, 2024.

Story from a TV Meteorologist

Jeremy Lewan, meteorologist at WNEP in Central PA collected GLOBE Eclipse data on the M.S. Zaandam cruising off the coast of Mazatlan, Mexico. He provided what was almost certainly the first GLOBE Eclipse observation from totality on April 8. He [reported about the trip on his news station on April 18](#) in which he talks about his eclipse data and shows a graph he put together of the data, with some excellent shoutouts to GLOBE and NASA.

GLOBE Observer Website

NESEC highlighted the eclipse on the GLOBE Observer website throughout the last half of 2023 and through 2024. The web page included an eclipse landing page with information about how to participate in GLOBE Eclipse. As mentioned earlier, the website also served as a repository for all GLOBE Eclipse resources.

Between June 2023 and May 8, 2024, the website received 319,845 views from 109,696 unique users. In that time, the most viewed pages were the home page, get the app, and the eclipse landing page. Other top pages that received more than 1,000 views include (in order of popularity): Do GLOBE Observer, Do GLOBE Observer - clouds, Eclipse toolkit, Clouds science, Eclipse taking observations, Eclipse Resource Library, Get Data - Eclipse, Eclipse - Data Analysis, Eclipse 2017 Data, and Eclipse Media Kit. This indicates that the eclipse drove people to the GLOBE Observer website.

Page (Top 12 for timeframe*, with consolidations, plus other eclipse-related pages)	Views (01 June 2023 - 08 May 2024)	Users (01 June 2023 - 08 May 2024)
Total	319,845	109,692
Home page*	62,584	34,571
Get the App*	37,845	20,940

Eclipse*	30,061	18,538
Eclipse Challenge*	20,505	13,401
Do GLOBE Observer*	10,941	5,568
Do GO - Clouds*	7,903	3,470
Eclipse Toolkit*	6,299	2,497
Clouds Science*	6,275	3,710
Eclipse - Taking Observations*	5,898	2,657
Eclipse - Resource Library*	5,060	1,938
Get Data - Eclipse	2,131	1,063
Eclipse - Data Analysis	1,298	604
Eclipse 2017 Data	1,183	582
Eclipse Media Kit	1,146	509

Peak traffic to the website occurred on April 8, 2024, with additional peaks on March 15, April 5, and May 4.

Eclipse Data

GLOBE Observer Growth

All outreach activities did bring new volunteers to GLOBE during both the October and April eclipses with the biggest gains happening in April.

GLOBE Observer Eclipse Data

This table summarizes all data collected during the eclipses as of August 2024. Civil Air Patrol paper data is not included (see below).

Grouping	Air Temp - Oct 14	Air Temp - Apr 08	All Air Temp	Land Cover - Oct 14	Land Cover - Apr 08	All Land Cover	Clouds - Oct 14	Clouds - Apr 08	All Clouds
Total data points	17808	32385	50193	130	631	761	2258	6991	9249
Total plus pending CAP	17808	42805	60613	130	631	761	2258	23142	25400
Weather stations (Air Temp)	12790	13478	26268	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
Non-weather stations (Air Temp)	5018	29327	34345	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
Via Eclipse tool (Air Temp)	4393	17172	21565	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
Via GO (Clouds/LC)	n/a	n/a	n/a	130	631	761	2247	6962	9209

Data collected by GLOBE teams provide an indication about how much data came from partner-supported outreach, since teams are organized groups led by a facilitator of some sort.

The April total eclipse in particular benefitted from partner-led data collection. Civil Air Patrol Pending refers to data from most Civil Air Patrol classrooms, which was collected on paper and is still being uploaded to the database. CAP observations are from all 50 states, Washington DC, Puerto Rico, and 2 Canadian provinces, providing significant data away from the path of totality.

Data Associated with Teams	Air Temp - Oct 14	Air Temp - Apr 08	All Air Temp	Land Cover - Oct 14	Land Cover - Apr 08	All Land Cover	Clouds - Oct 14	Clouds - Apr 14	All Clouds
Civil Air Patrol (all)	363	14441	14804	11	167	178	115	18340	18455
Civil Air Patrol Squadrons	363	3987	4350	11	167	178	115	2159	2274
CAP Solar Eclipse Classroom	n/a	34	34	n/a	0	0	n/a	30	30
CAP Pending	0	10420	10420	0	0	0	0	16151	16151
Eclipse Educators (TMN)	203	318	521	4	7	11	53	71	124
GLOBE Eclipse Libraries	220	609	829	6	16	22	72	117	189
All libraries (includes GELs)	549	1044	1593	9	30	39	191	203	394
Eclipse Workshop 2024 (LaRC)	n/a	655	655	n/a	19	19	n/a	316	316
Solar Eclipse PD (Mission Earth)	184	331	515	4	3	7	26	95	121
Colombia Eclipse 2023 (Colombia CC)	93	0	93	2	n/a	2	27	n/a	27
Other Eclipse teams (not counted elsewhere)	16	139	155	0	2	2	3	30	33
Data points entered by Kristen Weaver on behalf of other users	248	789	1037						
Total Data Submitted by Teams	1876	18326	20202	36	244	280	115	19172	19659

Overall, partner-led data collection was significant during both eclipses. Just under 64 percent of clouds and air temperature data (excluding weather station data) came from partners. Partner participation was more significant during the April total solar eclipse, during which more than 62 percent of manually submitted air temperature data (excluding weather station data) and 77 percent of cloud data came from partners. Of these, Civil Air Patrol is the most active partnership, providing more than 33 percent of all air temperature data, including weather station data, and nearly 80 percent of cloud data during the April eclipse.

Analysis of Team Data	Air Temp - Oct 14	Air Temp - Apr 08	All Air Temp	Land Cover - Oct 14	Land Cover - Apr 08	All Land Cover	Clouds - Oct 14	Clouds - Apr 14	All Clouds
Team Data % of Non-Weather Station Data	37.39%	62.49%	58.82%	27.69%	38.67%	36.79%	5.09%	82.85%	77.40%
CAP Percent of total data	2.04%	33.74%	24.42%	8.46%	26.47%	23.39%	5.09%	79.25%	72.66%
Team data % of whole (including CAP)	10.53%	42.81%	33.33%	27.69%	38.67%	36.79%	5.09%	82.85%	77.40%

Data Analysis and Archive

We published the eclipse dataset on the [GLOBE Observer Eclipse data page](#).

Ashlee Autore is analyzing the eclipse data and will present results at the Fall Meeting of the American Geophysical Union in December 2024.

Post-Eclipse Activities

Ashlee Autore is analyzing the eclipse data and will present results at the Fall Meeting of the American Geophysical Union. Initial results indicate the formation of high cirrus clouds or contrails during the eclipse in certain regions and conditions.

We presented the eclipse data and summary activities at:

- The American Meteorological Society (January 2024)
- The summer meeting of the American Astronomical Society, June 10-11
- The GLOBE Annual Meeting (facilitated an eclipse session), July 2024
- Civil Air Patrol Annual Conference, August 2024
- Fall American Geophysical Union Meeting, December 2024

We contributed to the Science Activation summary paper about eclipse activities being submitted to the Bulletin of the American Astronomical Society.

Lessons Learned

The eclipse provided a few insights to improve science engagement going forward:

- Engage through partners to extend reach and to provide better long-term support for volunteers
 - Facilitators or partners need support, including training and opportunities to share their ideas and experience.
 - Partners that have complementary goals are ideal. In these cases, co-facilitated partnerships develop easily because our objectives fill a need to meet their objectives, resulting in the best outcomes. The Civil Air Patrol is a prime example of this.
- Offline, non-digital engagement works best on site during an event. Provide both digital and non-digital ways to engage.
- Create foundational resources that can be leveraged for various partnerships. The resources might be adapted for individual partnership needs. For example, Civil Air Patrol recreated paper data sheets to suit their needs, but they had the original NESEC resource to guide them.
- Offer content in the most common languages of the audience. Our Spanish content was extremely popular. Civil Air Patrol also indicated that it greatly impacted native Spanish speakers, who reported the most significant shift in interest toward STEM careers as a result of participating in the Eclipse mission in their own language.

Conclusion

We conclude that the partnership approach encouraged and enabled through Science Activation was highly successful. External partnerships were also critical to the success of GLOBE Eclipse. While the United States will not experience another eclipse for many years, this approach could be a model for successful event-driven outreach that includes diverse populations.